

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION OF INTERFACIAL FAILURE CRITERION IN A GLASS FIBER/EPOXY COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

In fiber reinforced composite materials, the interface between the fiber and the matrix plays a key role in mechanical properties of composite materials. Therefore, a more accurate evaluation method of the interface is necessary to develop better fiber reinforced composite materials. Many techniques are used for evaluating the interfacial properties. An interfacial strength evaluation method using cruciform specimens has a feature that it can avoid the influence of the stress singularity at the free edge [1]. In the present study, the relation between the interfacial tensile stress and the interfacial shear stress is examined. A GF/Epoxy model composite is used. The initiation and propagation of interfacial debonding are experimentally clarified. Moreover, stress analysis using finite element method (FEM) is conducted.

2 Experiment

A glass fiber (17 μ m in the diameter) was used as the reinforcement. Epoxy resin (jER 828) was used as the matrix material with TETA (Triethylenetetramine) as a hardener. In the present study, both room temperature cured and high temperature cured specimens were used. The curing time of the specimen of the room temperature cured specimen was assumed to be one week. Moreover, in the high temperature cured specimens, it was cured under the condition shown in Figure 1 (80 minutes cure at 100°C followed by 60 minutes cure at 50°C). After curing, the specimens were cooled to the room temperature within about 8 hours.

Cruciform specimens with fibers whose angles between the loading direction were 90°, 67.5°, 45°, 35° and 22.5° are used. In this work, each specimen is referred to as cruciform- φ specimen, where φ is the angle between the fiber and loading directions, which we refer to as cruciform angle. Figure 2 shows the specimen geometry. In each specimen, tension test was conducted with a small loading machine installed on the stage of an optical microscope. During loading, interfacial debonding initiation and the progress was observed. The crosshead speed was 0.05mm/min.

3 Results and Discussion

Figure 3 shows the initiation and progress of the interfacial debonding observed in (a) cruciform-90 and (b) cruciform-67.5 specimens (room temperature cured specimens). Similar debonding initiation and progress behavior is also observed in cruciform-45 and cruciform-35 specimens. However, in cruciform-22.5 specimens, no debonding initiation was observed, that is, specimen final fracture occurred before the debonding initiation. It was found that as the cruciform angle gets smaller, the debonding initiation specimen average stress gets higher.

We considered the stress state at a point in the fiber/matrix interface. To describe the interfacial *tensile* and *shear* stresses, we define another three-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system, x' - y' - z' coordinate system, as shown in Figure 4. We take the tangential direction of the interface as x' -direction and the normal direction to the interface as y' -direction at a point in the interface as also shown

in Figure 4. z' -direction coincides with z -direction. We also define the angle θ which the line from the fiber center and a point in the interface forms from the specimen thickness direction (x -direction) to specify the stress evaluation site.

The normal stress in y' -direction at an interface point, $\sigma_{y'y'}$ is the interfacial normal stress. The interfacial shear stress can be written by

$\sqrt{\tau_{x'y'}^2 + \tau_{y'z'}^2}$. Because the stress we can measure is the average specimen stress, we are interested in the relation between the average specimen stress and the interfacial stresses. We defined the *normalized interfacial normal and shear stresses*, S_n and S_s , respectively, as

$$S_n = \frac{\sigma_{y'y'}}{\sigma} \quad (1)$$

$$S_s = \frac{\sqrt{\tau_{x'y'}^2 + \tau_{y'z'}^2}}{\sigma} \quad (2)$$

which are the ratio of the interfacial stresses to the average specimen stresses, σ , which can be derived by the applied load and the specimen cross sectional area where the specimen width is *not* enlarged.

Although we conducted both the cruciform specimen test by varying the cruciform angles to observe the interfacial debonding initiation and FEM analysis to obtain the stress distribution to examine the relationship between the interfacial normal and shear stresses at debonding, it is very difficult to determine the point where the interfacial failure initiates because the diameter of the fiber is very small. Therefore we considered two interfacial failure criteria to discuss the point where the interfacial failure initiates, and we consider the procedure to determine the interfacial failure criterion based on the experimental results. Figure 5 shows schematics of (a) the quadratic failure criterion and (b) parabolic failure criterion which are described by

$$\left(\frac{\langle t_n \rangle}{Y_n}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_s}{Y_s}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{t_n}{Y_n} + \left(\frac{t_s}{Y_s}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (4)$$

where t_n is interfacial normal stress, t_s interfacial shear stress, Y_n the interfacial tensile strength, Y_s the interfacial shear strength, and $\langle \rangle$ is the McAuley bracket.

It is necessary to determine the point where the interfacial debonding initiates. In the present study, we considered two interfacial failure criteria as shown in Figure 5. First, the quadratic failure criterion is considered. Equation (3) can be rearranged to

$$Y_n = \sqrt{\langle t_n \rangle^2 + \left(\frac{t_s}{\alpha}\right)^2} \quad (5)$$

where we introduced a parameter α which can be defined by

$$\alpha = \frac{Y_s}{Y_n} \quad (6)$$

which is the ratio of the interfacial shear strength, Y_s , to the interfacial tensile strength, Y_n . Normalized interfacial normal and shear stresses can be written by

$$k_n(\theta) = t_n(\theta) / \sigma_{spe} \quad (7)$$

$$k_s(\theta) = t_s(\theta) / \sigma_{spe} \quad (8)$$

where σ_{spe} is the average specimen stress, and both the normalized interfacial stresses and the interfacial stresses are expressed explicitly as functions of the angle θ . Equations (7) and (8) are substituted into Equation (6) which results in

$$Y_n = \sqrt{\{k_n(\theta)\}^2 + \left\{\frac{k_s(\theta)}{\alpha}\right\}^2} \cdot \sigma_{spe} \quad (9)$$

where the relation between the interfacial tensile stress, Y_n , and the experimentally-obtained average specimen stress at interfacial debonding, σ_{spe} . Now, we define a function $F(a, \theta)$ as

$$F(\alpha, \theta) = \sqrt{\{k_n(\theta)\}^2 + \left\{\frac{k_s(\theta)}{\alpha}\right\}^2} \quad (10)$$

and we refer to as the equivalent normalized interfacial stress. In the parabolic failure criterion, $F(a, \theta)$ can be written as

$$F(\alpha, \theta) = \frac{k_n(\theta) + \sqrt{\{k_n(\theta)\}^2 + 4\left\{\frac{k_s(\theta)}{\alpha}\right\}^2}}{2} \quad (11)$$

Using the experimental data and the procedure proposed in the present study, we can derive the relation between the stress state and interfacial debonding initiation. Figure 6 shows the relation between the normal and shear stresses at debonding initiation. This can be interpreted as the interfacial failure envelope (interfacial failure criterion). We use both the quadratic and the parabolic criterion. If we assume that $\alpha = Y_s/Y_n = 1.5$ (Y_s : interfacial shear strength, Y_n : interfacial tensile strength), $Y_n = 26\text{MPa}$ in the case of the quadratic failure criterion and 28MPa in the case of the parabolic failure criterion for the room temperature cured specimens. Similarly, in the high temperature cured specimen, if we assume that $\alpha = 0.5$, $Y_n = 94\text{MPa}$ in the case of the quadratic failure criterion and 104MPa in the case of the parabolic failure criterion.

4 CONCLUSIONS

We conducted cruciform specimen test by varying the cruciform angles to make various interfacial stress state for glass fiber/epoxy composite. We determined the interfacial failure initiation location by introducing two interfacial failure criteria, the quadratic failure criterion and the parabolic failure criterion, using the experimentally-obtained debonding initiation stress and FEM results. It was implied that the value of the interfacial shear strength is higher than that of the tensile strength,

and that the interfacial failure initiates from $\theta = 90^\circ$ location for all cruciform specimens tested in this work.

References

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Figure 1. Program of curing at high temperature

Figure 2. Schematic of cruciform specimens. (a) cruciform-90, (b) cruciform-67.5, (c) cruciform-45, (d) cruciform-35 and (e) cruciform-22.5

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Debonding initiation and progress in (a) Cruciform-90 and (b) Cruciform-67.5 specimens (room temperature)

Figure 4. Stress evaluation site

Figure 5. Schematic of interfacial failure criteria. (a) Quadratic failure criterion and (b) parabolic failure criterion.

Figure 6. Interfacial failure envelopes (criteria) with experimental results